

ISic3512

I.Sicily inscription 3512

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Necropolis of San Placido

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale
interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3558

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI313628

1. Κλωδία Σε-

2. βῆρα ἔζησ-

3. σεν²⁶ ἔζησεν²⁶ ἔτη □ ις'.

4. □ □

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493842

EDCS 38200003

PHI 313628

Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At 5
Orsi, P. 1916. Messana. La necropoli romana di S. Placido e di altre scoperte avvenute nel 1910-1915. *Monumenti Antichi*. 24: 121-218. At 134

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